

AmbAu: Accurate and Robust Physical Layer Authentication for Ambient Backscatter Devices

Yifan Zhang*, Yongchao Dang*, Yishan Yang[†], Masoud Kaveh*, Zheng Yan[†], Riku Jäntti*

*Department of Information and Communications Engineering, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland

[†]School of Cyber Engineering, Xidian University, Xi'an, China

Email: yifan.l.zhang@aalto.fi, yongchao.dang@aalto.fi, ysyangxd@stu.xidian.edu.cn, masoud.kaveh@aalto.fi, zyan@xidian.edu.cn, riku.jantti@aalto.fi

Abstract—Ambient backscatter communication (AmBC) has become increasingly popular for facilitating ubiquitous Internet of Things (IoT) due to its ultra-low-power consumption and energy-harvesting capabilities. However, the open nature of wireless channels and the resource-limited devices in AmBC systems expose them to threats such as identity impersonation and wireless spoofing attacks. Recently, physical layer authentication (PLA) offered a lightweight solution to address the above security challenges by utilizing inherent wireless properties, like channel fading and signal patterns, as unique fingerprints to identify legitimate devices and distinguish them from attackers. Despite its promise, current research still lacks an effective PLA mechanism that can accurately authenticate backscatter devices (BDs) and defend against spoofing attacks in AmBC systems. This paper presents AmbAu, a two-stage PLA scheme designed to authenticate BDs by leveraging the signal correlation between an ambient source and the BD. In the initialization stage, the verifier extracts a complex covariance matrix from the downlink signals between the ambient source and the BD. This matrix is later used during the authentication stage to verify the BD's identity and detect spoofing attempts. Through security analysis, we demonstrate AmbAu's resilience against replay, relay, and counterfeiting attacks. Simulations under various conditions demonstrate AmbAu's accuracy, efficiency, and superior performance when compared to traditional PLA schemes.

Index Terms—Ambient backscatter communications, physical layer authentication, spoofing attack, Internet of Things.

I. INTRODUCTION

Backscatter communication (BC) is a cutting-edge technology driving the widespread adoption of the Internet of Things (IoT) [1]. It allows battery-free or energy-constrained backscatter devices (BDs) to harvest energy from surrounding electromagnetic waves and transmit data by reflecting incident radio frequency (RF) signals, which significantly improves spectrum efficiency. In a typical BC system, known as monostatic BC (MoBC) [2], a dedicated transceiver transmits signals to power the BD and receives its backscattered signals for communication. While MoBC offers precise control over communication, the requirement for a dedicated transceiver increases system costs. To address this limitation, ambient backscatter communication (AmBC) has emerged. AmBC allows BDs to harvest energy from ambient RF sources (e.g., Wi-Fi and TV signals) and communicate with independent receivers. This eliminates the need for dedicated RF sources, which aligns better with the growing demands of the IoT, en-

abling applications like relay transmission, medical telemetry, and cost-effective sensor networks [3].

Despite its energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness, BC faces significant security challenges. The open nature of wireless channels allows malicious devices to intercept a BD's backscattered signals, further allowing them to impersonate the BD to deceive other devices. In addition, these vulnerabilities are exacerbated by the limited computational resources of BDs, which make it impractical for them to use conventional cryptographic methods that rely on complex encryption algorithms and hash functions [4]. Recently, physical layer authentication (PLA) has emerged as a promising solution to these security concerns. By leveraging the unique characteristics of the wireless medium as authentication fingerprints, PLA allows verifiers to authenticate legitimate devices (e.g., BDs) and detect potential impersonators. Then, the verifier can block unauthorized access, which provides a critical line of defense against security threats.

Several PLA schemes have been proposed for BC systems, which can be generally categorized into device-based and channel-based approaches. Device-based methods exploit manufacturing imperfections in BDs. For instance, Narayanan et al. [5] showed that energy harvesting creates a unique discharge pattern on a BD's oscillator, serving as an authentication fingerprint to prevent impersonation. Similarly, Li et al. [2] used a BD's reflection coefficient to establish a unique fingerprint. However, extracting these features requires complex analyzers, which increases hardware and computational costs. Channel-based schemes exploit the spatial decorrelation of wireless channels to authenticate BDs based on location. Luo et al. [6] used received signal strength (RSS) to build sensitive propagation signatures for authenticating on-body BDs, while Wang et al. [7] combined RSS and angle of arrival to both authenticate BDs and track attackers using spatial information. In another study, Li et al. [8] leveraged multipath gains from ambient BDs to authenticate ambient sources in a non-orthogonal multiple access symbiotic network. Although channel-based features simplify hardware, they remain vulnerable to spoofing attacks, such as relay, replay, and counterfeiting, which can compromise security by continuously observing the BD's backscattering pattern [7].

Despite many PLA proposals in BC systems, three issues persist. First, existing schemes cannot directly authenticate

BDs in AmBC systems. Most works [2], [6], [7], [9] address traditional MoBC scenarios, where a dedicated signal interacts with the BD to extract identity features from the backscattered round-trip signal, while PLS in AmBC is underexplored, where the BD’s signal mixes with random ambient signals. Although [8] considers AmBC, its focus is on using BDs for multipath gain or embedding tags to aid ambient source authentication, whereas AmbAu targets direct BD authentication. Second, many PLA schemes neglect wireless spoofing attacks (replay, relay, counterfeiting) that mimic physical-layer features, often focusing on upper-layer defenses instead. Third, many schemes depend on high-complexity techniques. For example, device-based PLA requires expensive analyzers, and channel-based PLA depends on precise channel estimation. Therefore, a PLA scheme that accurately authenticates BDs in AmBC systems, robustly defends against spoofing attacks, and operates with low computational overhead is crucial.

To address the issues outlined above, this paper proposes AmbAu, a lightweight PLA scheme specifically designed to authenticate BDs in AmBC systems. We model a downlink AmBC system where an ambient source continuously broadcasts signals that illuminate a BD. The BD then backscatter data to an independent verifier equipped with multiple antennas. The authentication process consists of two stages: an initialization stage and an authentication stage. During the initialization stage, the verifier uses its multi-antenna array to separate the mixed signals from both the ambient source and the BD. It then calculates the correlation between these signals, storing the result as a unique authentication fingerprint. This fingerprint integrates the characteristics of both the ambient source and the BD, which makes it difficult for attackers to imitate. In the authentication stage, the verifier recalculates the fingerprint from newly received signals and compares it with the stored fingerprint to authenticate the BD and detect any unauthorized access. By directly extracting the fingerprint from the received signals, AmbAu eliminates the need for complex channel estimation and costly signal analyzers, offering a low-complexity solution.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized below:

- 1) We propose AmbAu, a PLA scheme that allows an independent verifier to authenticate BDs by leveraging the correlation between the BD signal and the ambient signal in an AmBC system. AmbAu avoids channel estimation and complex signal analyzer, maintaining a low complexity.
- 2) We perform a comprehensive security analysis to demonstrate AmbAu’s robustness against impersonation attacks and common wireless spoofing attacks, including replay, relay, and counterfeiting.
- 3) We validate AmbAu’s accuracy and efficiency through numerical simulations under various system parameters. Furthermore, we compare AmbAu with conventional PLA schemes to highlight its superior performance.

Organization: The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the system and adversary models

Fig. 1. System model and potential attacks.

for AmbAu. Section III describes the authentication process and provides a security analysis of AmbAu. In Section IV, we assess AmbAu’s performance. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

Notations: The notation $\mathcal{CN}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ refers to the circularly symmetric complex Gaussian (CSCG) distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 . For a given vector, $\|\cdot\|_{l1}$ represents the 1-norm, and $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute value operation. The Dirac delta function is represented by $\delta(\cdot)$. The complex conjugate of the received signal y is denoted as y^* , and $E[X]$ represents the expected value of X . The notation $O(L)$ indicates time complexity, which means the running time scales linearly with the input size L .

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this section, we introduce the system setup of AmbAu in the system model and analyze the capabilities of potential attacks in the adversary model.

A. System Model

We consider a general AmBC system with downlink channels, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The system consists of an ambient RF source (S) that transmits ambient RF signals, a passive BD (B) awaiting being authenticated, and a receiver (R) equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) for authenticating the BD. The wireless channel between devices L and K is assumed to experience Rayleigh fading due to the effects of multipath propagation and complex environments. Thus, The channel impulse response is defined as:

$$h_{L,K}(t) = |h_{L,K}|e^{j\phi_{L,K}}\delta(t - \tau_{L,K}), \quad (1)$$

where $L, K \in \{S, B, R\}$, j is the imaginary unit, $\phi_{L,K} \in [0, 2\pi]$ denotes the phase shift due to carrier frequency offsets, and $\tau_{L,K}$ represents the propagation delay on the L - K link.

In the system, the BD first harvests energy from surrounding electromagnetic waves and then transmits information to the receiver by reflecting the incident ambient signals from S . The receiver then captures a combination of signals from both the ambient source and the BD. The received signals can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \sqrt{P}h_{S,R}(t)s(t) + \sqrt{P}\eta h_{S,B}(t)h_{B,R}(t)s(t) + n(t) \quad (2)$$

where $s(t)$ is a random signal transmitted by S with an average power P [10]. The factor η represents the modulation loss in the BD where $\eta \in (0, 1]$. The noise term, $n(t) \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2)$,

denotes complex additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance σ^2 . To simplify, we use $y_d(t) = \sqrt{P}h_{S,R}(t)s(t)$ to represent the original ambient signal directly from the RF source and $y_b(t) = \sqrt{P}\eta h_{S,B}(t)h_{B,R}(t)s(t)$ is the backscatter signal reflected from B . Thus, Eq. 2 can be represented as

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = y_d(t) + y_b(t) + n(t). \quad (3)$$

B. Adversary Model

In this work, we first consider an impersonation attacker who knows the upper-layer identity of a legitimate BD, such as its serial or reference number. It attempts to use this information to impersonate the legitimate BD. The impersonation attack operates at the upper layer and is the common target that PLA schemes wish to solve. Furthermore, at the physical layer, wireless spoofing attackers can intercept the RF signals of a legitimate BD and attempt to mimic its physical authentication features to bypass PLA at the verifier. As illustrated in Fig. 1, these attackers can generally be categorized into three types based on their methods for imitating the physical authentication features of the BD: *Attacker-1* conducts a replay attack by capturing the backscattered signals from a legitimate BD and retransmitting them unchanged to the receiver, tricking the receiver into believing a new authentication request has been initiated by the authorized BD. With a similar purpose, *Attacker-2* executes a relay attack by intercepting and instantly relaying the signals to the receiver without alteration. *Attacker-3* performs a counterfeiting attack by intercepting, recording, and analyzing the physical characteristics (e.g., amplitude and frequency) of the backscattered signals. The attacker then transmits falsified signals that imitates the authentication fingerprint to the receiver, posing as the legitimate BD. Additionally, two practical assumptions are commonly made in the adversary model of PLA schemes [6], [7]. First, the attacker cannot physically position itself within the immediate vicinity (within several wavelengths) of a legitimate BD. Second, the transmitting signals of two devices separated by more than half a wavelength are considered independent.

III. AMBAU DESIGN

In this section, we detail the AmbAu authentication process and perform a security analysis for AmbAu.

A. Initialization Stage

In the initialization stage, BDs transmit signals to the receiver through a secure communication link, such as in a controlled or air-gapped environment. The receiver collects the physical layer features of the BDs from their backscattered signals, creating a unique fingerprint for each BD. This information is then used to construct a whitelist, which will serve as a reference during the authentication stage.

Specifically, after receiving the signals described in Eq. 2, the receiver, equipped with the ULA, can apply techniques such as averaging power detection [11] or spatial diversity [12] to extract the backscattered link signals $y_b(t)$ and the direct link signals $y_d(t)$ from the mixed received signals. Then, for an easy understanding of our basic idea, let's assume there is no noise. To capture the unique feature of the BD, the receiver

calculates the covariance between the signal received from the BD and the signal from the ambient source to generate a unique fingerprint for the BD as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{B,S}(t) &= E[y_b(t)y_d^*(t)] \\ &= E[\sqrt{P}h_b(t)s(t)(\sqrt{P}\eta h_d(t)s(t))^*] \\ &= \eta P|h_b||h_d|E\left[e^{j\phi_b}\delta(t-\tau_b)s(t)\right. \\ &\quad \left.(e^{j\phi_a}\delta(t-\tau_d)s(t))^*\right], \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $h_d(t)$ represents the channel response of direct link $h_{S,R}(t)$ and $h_b(t)$ represents the cascade channel response of backscatter link $\eta h_{S,B}(t)h_{B,R}(t)$. $\eta P|h_b||h_d|$ is the extracted common real term. By performing conjugate operations on $e^{j\phi_a}$ and combining the Dirac delta function with the signal $s(t)$, the equation can be further expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} R_{B,S}(t) &= \eta P e^{j(\phi_b-\phi_a)}|h_b||h_d|E[s(t-\tau_b)s^*(t-\tau_d)] \\ &= \eta P e^{j(\phi_b-\phi_a)}|h_b||h_d|R_{SS}(t-(\tau_b-\tau_d)), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the self-correlation R_{SS} is derived from the assumption that $s(t)$ is wide-sense stationary signal.

Remark 1: From Eq. 5, we can find that the value of $R_{B,S}$ depends on the modulation loss η , the transmission power P , the phase difference $\Delta\phi = (\phi_b - \phi_a)$, and the propagation delay difference $\Delta\tau = (\tau_b - \tau_d)$ between the direct link and the backscattered link, since other factors usually keep constant during communications. According to the law of large numbers, the value of $R_{B,S}^{M_1 M_2}$ converges to a stable value after multiple communication cycles, and it is different between BDs due to the fact that they experience different channel responses. Thus, this value is used as the unique fingerprint to distinguish different BDs.

Furthermore, to capture rich features of the BD, the receiver computes a covariance matrix that incorporates the signals received from both the ambient source and the BD across all antenna elements. The resulting metric is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}_{B,S} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{B,S}^{11} & \cdots & R_{B,S}^{1M} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ R_{B,S}^{M1} & \cdots & R_{B,S}^{MM} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where each element in the metric represents the covariance between the signal from S received at the M_1 th antenna and the signal from B received at the M_2 th antenna. By computing this covariance matrix, the receiver collects multiple samples of covariance features for the BD, thereby enhancing the richness and uniqueness of the BD's fingerprint, since each element is a unique feature for the BD. This makes it hard for the attacker to accurately imitate the multiple covariance samples contained in the metric.

B. Authentication Stage

The receiver can authenticate a BD in the authentication stage by comparing the BD's fingerprint extracted from the current transmission with the fingerprint stored in the initialization stage. The process of extracting the BD's fingerprint

follows a similar procedure to that in the initialization stage. After harvesting sufficient energy, the BD backscatters the ambient signals to the receiver for identification. Referring to Eq. 4-6, the receiver derives the BD's fingerprint calculated at the authentication stage, denoted as $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S}$. The receiver can then authenticate the BD by comparing the extracted fingerprint $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S}$ with the previously stored fingerprint $\mathbf{R}_{B,S}$.

$$\|\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S} - \mathbf{R}_{B,S}\|_{L_1} \underset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\geq}} \delta, \quad (7)$$

where the value of δ represents the threshold for making the authentication decision. \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 represent binary hypothesis tests of the authentication failure and the authentication success, respectively. Specifically, they can be denoted as

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{H}_0 : \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S} = \mathbf{R}_{A,S} + \mathbf{E}_{A,S} \\ \mathcal{H}_1 : \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S} = \mathbf{R}_{B,S} + \mathbf{E}_{B,S}, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{A,S}$ represents that the extracted fingerprint is from an attacker. The terms $\mathbf{E}_{A,S}$ and $\mathbf{E}_{B,S}$ represent estimation error at the receiver for $\mathbf{R}_{A,S}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{B,S}$, respectively. They are caused by AWGN. If $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S}$ is from a legitimate BD, it should closely match $\mathbf{R}_{B,S}$, with only minor differences caused by the noise. Conversely, the extracted fingerprint from an attacker will significantly differ from the stored one due to the varying positions and the location-decorrection of the covariance matrix. As a result, the receiver can authenticate the BD by detecting any significant discrepancies between $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{B,S}$:

Remark II: The proper selection of the threshold δ in Eq. 7 is critical to AmbAu's performance. For example, relaxing the threshold can help the receiver correctly identify legitimate BDs, but it also increases the vulnerability of potential attackers bypassing the authentication process successfully. In Section IV, we adjust the threshold to demonstrate the trade-off between AmbAu's ability to correctly identify legitimate BDs and the potential for mistakenly accepting unauthorized devices.

Using covariance metrics as the fingerprint, AmbAu is lightweight, accurate, and robust. The time complexity of AmbAu is primarily determined by the computation of the covariance matrix, which is $O(L \times M^2)$ where L represents the length of the signal and M denotes the number of antennas. This is because calculating the covariance between the signals of BD and the signals of the ambient source requires $O(L)$ complexity, and the matrix includes M^2 times calculation from M antenna elements. Since both L and M are typically predefined in practical scenarios, the time complexity of AmbAu can be regarded as a quadratic function of a constant. In addition, by combining the feature of the signal from the ambient source and the BD, we believe AmbAu can achieve accurate BD identification and perform robustly against various attacks. In what follows, we perform a security analysis for AmbAu.

C. Security Analysis

In this part, we theoretically analyze the robustness of AmbAu under various attacks, including impersonation, replay, relay, and counterfeiting attacks.

1) *Impersonation Attacks:* AmbAu can naturally resist impersonation attacks, as the physical-layer features are exploited as the authentication fingerprint to identify impersonation attackers. Impersonation attackers aim to pass the identification mechanism of the BC system by imitating the upper-layer identity of a legitimate BD without the ability to manipulate and imitate wireless signals from the legitimate BD. Therefore, AmbAu can easily identify impersonation attacks by comparing the covariance feature of a BD with the stored information at the physical layer.

2) *Replay Attacks:* AmbAu can resist replay attacks due to additional replaying channels introduced by the attacker. The attacker can capture a legitimate BD's authentication request signals, represented as $A(t_1) = \sqrt{P}\eta h_{S,B}(t_1)h_{B,A}(t_1)s(t_1)$. Then, the attacker could record this signal and re-transmit it to the receiver at a later time t_2 , represented by $A(t_2) = h_{A,R}(t_2)A(t_1)$. If the attacker is located at a sufficient distance ($d > \frac{\lambda}{2}$) from the BD and the receiver, $h_{B,A}(t_1)h_{A,R}(t_2)$ will be uncorrelated with $h_{B,R}(t_1)$. Thus, $A(t_2) \neq y_d(t)$. This allows the receiver to resist replay attacks by comparing the fingerprints of the received signals with those stored in the whitelist.

3) *Relay Attacks:* AmbAu can detect the presence of a relay attacker due to the de-correlation of the relay channel and the legitimate channel. Even if a powerful relay attacker positioned near the BD manages to block and imitate the propagation delay of the BD's signal, the received signal at the receiver still propagates through a different cascade channel from the legitimate BD to the attacker and then to the receiver, denoted as $A(t) = \sqrt{P}\eta h_{S,B}(t)h_{B,A}(t)h_{A,R}(t)s(t)$. Obviously, $A(t) \neq y_d(t)$. The additional forwarding link through the attacker causes additional phase shifts and power degradation in $h_{B,A}(t)h_{A,R}(t)$ compared to $h_{B,R}(t)$. As a result, the calculated covariance feature at the receiver is different from those stored in the whitelist.

4) *Counterfeiting Attacks:* AmbAu can resist counterfeiting attacks, as the attacker cannot accurately imitate the time feature in the fingerprint. For example, even if an ideal counterfeiter manages to imitate the power characteristics of the BD signal captured by the receiver, additional processing time is required to analyze the BD's transmitted signal. Therefore, in AmbAu, the receiver can prevent unauthorized access by preemptively accepting the first valid authentication request.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section evaluates AmbAu's performance in terms of authentication accuracy and efficiency under various simulation parameters, including signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), the distance between the attacker and BD, and the number of antennas. Additionally, a comparison between AmbAu and conventional PLA schemes is provided.

Fig. 2. ROC of authentication under various SNR conditions.

A. Evaluation Setup

1) *Evaluation Metrics*: Authentication accuracy pertains to the accurate identification of a BD, involving the acceptance of legitimate BDs and the rejection of attackers. Following the guidelines in [4], [7], two accuracy metrics are defined: **true positive rate (TPR)**, which represents the proportion of legitimate BDs correctly accepted by AmbAu from all authentication requests, and the **false positive rate (FPR)**, which denotes the proportion of attackers incorrectly accepted by AmbAu among all authentication requests. Additionally, the **receiver operating characteristic (ROC)** curve is used to visualize the trade-off between TPR and FPR across different authentication thresholds. Efficiency measures the influence of the size of the experimental parameters on the calculation time of AmbAu. The efficiency is evaluated through a theoretical **time complexity** analysis and experimental simulations of the processing time of AmbAu.

2) *Simulation Setting*: We simulate a downlink AmBC system consisting of an ambient RF source, a BD, and a multi-antenna receiver. The distance between two distinct devices is set at 2 meters. Additionally, an attacker is positioned within a 0.5-meter radius of the BD. The attacker impersonates a legitimate BD by intercepting upper-layer identity information and attempting to inject illegal messages during communication between the legitimate BD and the receiver. The communication channel between the devices follows the Rayleigh channel model. By default, the SNR is set to 5 dB, the carrier frequency is 900 MHz, the number of antennas at the receiver (M) is 4, and the ambient source transmits with power $P = 1$ dBm. The signal length (L) is set to 10^6 during the initialization stage and reduced to 10^5 during the authentication phase. This is because the initialization stage generally has a longer duration than the authentication stage in practice. Meanwhile, the long signal length in the initialization and authentication stages ensures the receiver can collect a stable fingerprint based on its statistical characteristics. To ensure reliability, 1,000 authentication processes are repeated for each simulation.

3) *Baselines*: Since AmbAu is the first PLA scheme specifically designed to authenticate BDs in AmBC systems, a direct comparison with PLA works designed for MoBC systems would be unfair, as MoBC systems involve dedicated and controllable transmitters. Instead, we select conventional channel-

Fig. 3. ROC of authentication under various numbers of attackers and distance between the attacker and the BD.

Fig. 4. ROC of authentication under various numbers of antenna at the receiver.

based PLA schemes where **Baseline 1** [13] uses RSS as the authentication fingerprint and **Baseline 2** [14] uses channel state information (CSI) as the authentication fingerprint. Given their low complexity requirements for the authenticated device (i.e., BD), these schemes can be adapted for use in AmBC systems. These two schemes are simulated using the same settings as AmbAu in our evaluation.

B. Simulation Results

1) *Authentication Accuracy*: Fig. 2 presents ROC curves under various SNR values within the range [0, 20]. Each point on the curve represents a TPR and a FPR value at different threshold δ . The figure shows that the TPR improves as the FPR increases, indicating that the BD can achieve a desired TPR by selecting an appropriate threshold δ under a certain FPR limit. In addition, an increase in SNR results in a higher TPR at the same FPR, leading to improved authentication performance. Even in poor channel conditions with an SNR of 0 dB, the TPR remains above 0.9 in most cases, demonstrating that AmbAu can accurately identify different BDs in noisy environments.

In Fig. 3, we examine the effect of the number of attackers, as well as the distance between the attacker and the BD on AmbAu's accuracy. Two key observations can be made. First, the accuracy decreases as the number of attackers increases. This decline is attributed to the additional interference caused by multiple attackers, which complicates the receiver's ability to differentiate between signals originating from various locations. Second, the accuracy also diminishes as the attacker moves closer to the BD. The closer proximity leads to a higher correlation between the attacker's signals and the legitimate BD's signals, making it more difficult for the receiver to distinguish between them.

Fig. 4 shows the impact of the number of antennas on the accuracy under a poor SNR condition (SNR = 0 dB). It shows that accuracy improves as the number of antennas increases. This is because the multiple antennas provide spatial resolution, allowing the receiver to extract fingerprints more accurately. This finding highlights that AmbAu can achieve accuracy BD authentication by increasing the number of antennas, even in noisy environments. Particularly, a significant boost in ROC performance is observed when the number of antennas increases from 2 to 4, emphasizing the value of multi-antenna techniques.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF EFFICIENCY

Antenna Numbers	M=2	M=4	M=6	M=8	M=10
Initialization Stage (s)	1.39	3.90	7.99	11.06	14.66
Authentication Stage (s)	5.39e-3	2.06e-2	2.32e-2	3.14e-2	4.13e-2

TABLE II
COMPARISON BETWEEN CONVENTIONAL PLA WORKS AND AMBAU

Ref.	TPR	TC	CEA	Robustness			
				IA	RP	RL	CA
Baseline 1 (RSS) [13]	0.975	$O(K)$	✓	✓	×	×	×
Baseline 2 (CSI) [14]	0.853	$O(K)$	×	✓	✓	✓	×
AmbAu	0.99,8	$O(K^2)$	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

K: a constant number. TC: time complexity. CEA: channel estimation avoidance; IA: impersonation attack; RP: replay attack; RL: relay attack; CA: counterfeiting attack. The TPR value is tested under a FPR limit of 0.1.

2) *Authentication Efficiency*: Table I assesses AmbAu efficiency by measuring time consumption during the initialization and authentication stages with varying numbers of antennas. As expected, the time consumption of AmbAu increases with the number of antennas. This is because the increase in the number of antennas makes the receiver take more time to catch and process signals from multiple antennas. Fortunately, the time required for the authentication stage remains within a few milliseconds, which is acceptable for practical applications.

3) *Comparison with Baselines*: Compared to conventional PLA schemes proposed in Ref. [13] and Ref. [14], AmbAu demonstrates superior performance in terms of TPR, time complexity, avoidance of channel estimation, and robustness, using settings defined in Table II. Notably, AmbAu achieves a higher TPR than the baselines, highlighting its superior accuracy. This demonstrates that the combined feature of ambient source and backscatter devices is more accurate than the single feature in the authentication procedure. While AmbAu's time complexity is higher due to the use of multi-antenna techniques, this complexity is still quadratic with respect to a constant, making it accessible in practice. In addition, AmbAu shows strong robustness that can defend against impersonation, replay, relay, and counterfeiting attacks. This differs from the conventional schemes where Baseline 1 can only resist impersonation attacks and Baseline 2 fails to defend against counterfeiting attacks. Finally, AmbAu meets practical requirements by eliminating the need for channel estimation. As a result, we believe that AmbAu is highly accurate, robust and has great potential for practical applications.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces AmbAu, a lightweight PLA scheme designed to authenticate BDs in AmBC systems. AmbAu leverages the correlation between the signals from the ambient source and the BD as a joint fingerprint, avoiding channel estimation techniques and complex signal analyzers. Through comprehensive security analysis, we demonstrate that the joint fingerprint not only resists impersonation attacks targeting upper-layer identity but also performs robustly against wireless replay, relay, and counterfeiting attacks. Simulation results show that AmbAu can achieve high accuracy and efficiency under various channel conditions and parameter settings. It

also demonstrates the superiority of AmbAu over conventional PLA schemes. In future work, we plan to extend AmbAu to dynamic scenarios and explore its practical implementation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported in part by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant U23A20300; in part by the Key Research Project of Shaanxi Natural Science Foundation under Grant 2023-JC-ZD-35; in part by the Concept Verification Funding of Hangzhou Institute of Technology of Xidian University under Grant GNYZZ2024XX007; in part by the China 111 Project under Grant B16037; and in part by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101192113. (Corresponding author: Zheng Yan.).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Han, C. Qian, Y. Yang, G. Wang, H. Ding, X. Li, and K. Ren, "Butterfly: Environment-independent physical-layer authentication for passive RFID," *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, New York, United States, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 1–21, Dec. 2018.
- [2] J. Li, A. Li, D. Han, Y. Zhang, T. Li, and Y. Zhang, "RCID: Fingerprinting passive RFID tags via wideband backscatter," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM)*, London, United Kingdom, May 2022, pp. 700–709.
- [3] R. Duan, X. Wang, H. Yigitler, M. U. Sheikh, R. Jantti, and Z. Han, "Ambient backscatter communications for future ultra-low-power machine type communications: Challenges, solutions, opportunities, and future research trends," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 42–47, Feb. 2020.
- [4] D. Shan, K. Zeng, W. Xiang, P. Richardson, and Y. Dong, "PHY-CRAM: Physical layer challenge-response authentication mechanism for wireless networks," *IEEE Journal on selected areas in communications*, vol. 31, no. 9, pp. 1817–1827, Aug. 2013.
- [5] R. Narayanan, A. Varshney, and P. Papadimitratos, "Harvestprint: Securing battery-free backscatter tags through fingerprinting," in *ACM HotNets*, New York, NY, Nov. 2021, p. 178–184.
- [6] Z. Luo, W. Wang, J. Xiao, Q. Huang, T. Jiang, and Q. Zhang, "Authenticating on-body backscatter by exploiting propagation signatures," *Proc. ACM Interact. Mob. Wearable Ubiquitous Technol*, New York, United States, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 1–22, Sep. 2018.
- [7] P. Wang, Z. Yan, and K. Zeng, "BCAuth: Physical layer enhanced authentication and attack tracing for backscatter communications," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, vol. 17, pp. 2818–2834, 2022.
- [8] X. Li, Q. Wang, M. Zeng, Y. Liu, S. Dang, T. A. Tsiftsis, and O. A. Dobre, "Physical-layer authentication for ambient backscatter-aided noma symbiotic systems," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 2288–2303, 2023.
- [9] G. Wang, H. Cai, C. Qian, J. Han, S. Shi, X. Li, H. Ding, W. Xi, and J. Zhao, "Hu-fu: Replay-resilient rfid authentication," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Netw.*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 547–560, 2020.
- [10] P. Wang, L. Jiao, K. Zeng, and Z. Yan, "Physical layer key generation between backscatter devices over ambient rf signals," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2021*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–10.
- [11] G. Wang, F. Gao, R. Fan, and C. Tellambura, "Ambient backscatter communication systems: Detection and performance analysis," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 4836–4846, 2016.
- [12] A. M. Haimovich, R. S. Blum, and L. J. Cimini, "MIMO radar with widely separated antennas," *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 116–129, 2007.
- [13] Y. Sheng, K. Tan, G. Chen, D. Kotz, and A. Campbell, "Detecting 802.11 mac layer spoofing using received signal strength," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2008*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 1768–1776.
- [14] P. Baracca, N. Laurenti, and S. Tomasin, "Physical layer authentication over mimo fading wiretap channels," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 2564–2573, 2012.